

- Mapping Priority Areas for Electrification to Support Agriculture Growth and Food Security

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Executive Summary

This study applied geospatial analysis using the Energy Access Explorer (EAE) platform to identify priority areas in Zambia where expanded electricity access can most effectively support agricultural growth and food security. The analysis focuses on the intersection of agricultural activity, electricity access gaps, irrigation potential, infrastructure proximity, and development need, in line with national priorities to expand irrigation, improve productivity, and strengthen rural livelihoods.

Two scenarios were assessed to support differentiated electrification and financing strategies. Scenario 1 focuses on predominantly rural, rainfed agricultural areas with low electricity access and higher vulnerability. These areas are generally located far from existing grid infrastructure and show strong suitability for decentralized electrification solutions, particularly solar-based mini-grids and standalone systems. Electrification in these zones can enable irrigation development, reduce vulnerability to climate variability, and support climate-resilient agricultural intensification.

Scenario 2 focuses on areas with existing irrigated agriculture and closer proximity to electricity infrastructure. These areas are more suitable for grid extension and densification. Strengthening electricity access in these zones can improve the efficiency and reliability of irrigation systems and enable agro-processing, cold storage, and other value-adding activities that support agricultural commercialization and value chain development.

The integration of the Relative Wealth Index highlights areas where affordability constraints are likely to limit commercially driven electrification, strengthening the case for donor and concessional financing. The results provide a practical, spatially explicit basis for aligning electrification investments with agricultural development and food security objectives.

Overall, the study demonstrates the value of integrated energy–agriculture planning and provides evidence to support targeted electrification strategies that maximize development impact, promote inclusive growth, and strengthen food security in Zambia.

1. Introduction

Agriculture is a key pillar of Zambia's economy and food security, with a large proportion of the rural population dependent on smallholder farming. However, much of agricultural production remains rainfed and highly vulnerable to climate variability and drought. For example, during the 2024/2025 season the country experienced good rainfall resulting in crop production of approximately 4.0 million metric tons, an increase from the 1.5 million metric tons produced during the previous drought-induced season of 2023/2024. National agricultural development priorities emphasize the need to expand irrigated agriculture, improve productivity and strengthen agricultural value chains in order to enhance food security and rural incomes. At the same time, limited access to reliable electricity in many rural areas constrains the adoption of modern agricultural practices and productive uses of energy.

Zambia's electricity supply system comprises a national grid, complemented by off grid and mini grid systems. As of 2023, national electricity access stood at approximately 53.6 percent, with urban access at 80.3 percent and rural access at 34.0 percent, reflecting significant spatial disparities. About 34.0 percent of the population (20.8 million people) was connected to the main grid, while 19.6 percent accessed electricity through off-grid and mini-grid systems. The transmission and distribution network continues to expand, while decentralized solar based systems play an increasingly important role in extending access in rural and remote areas. Together, these grid and off-grid systems provide differentiated electrification pathways that are critical for supporting agricultural development and food security.

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This report focuses on the intersection of energy access and agricultural development in Zambia. It uses geospatial analysis to support evidence-based planning for electrification investments that can directly contribute to agricultural growth and food security.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to identify and map priority areas in Zambia where expanded electricity access can most effectively support agricultural productivity and food security. The specific objectives are to:

- Identify agricultural areas with low levels of electricity access and high potential for productive use of energy;
- Assess proximity to water resources and irrigation-related indicators to support electrification-enabled irrigation;
- Integrate development and vulnerability indicators to highlight zones where donor and concessional funding can have high development impact; and
- Provide insights to inform government agencies, donors and development partners on strategic electrification planning aligned with agricultural development priorities.

2. Methodology

2.1 Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented

The study applied a geospatial multi-criteria prioritization approach using the Energy Access Explorer (EAE) platform to support strategic electrification planning for agricultural development and food security in Zambia. EAE is a decision-support tool designed to integrate spatial datasets related to energy access, population distribution, infrastructure and socio-economic indicators to inform evidence-based planning. The platform was used to identify and prioritize areas where electricity access gaps overlap with agricultural activity and enabling conditions for productive use of energy. The approach supports strategic identification of high-impact zones for grid extension, mini-grid development and standalone renewable energy solutions, particularly in support of irrigation, agro-processing and other agricultural productive uses.

The steps undertaken during the study included:

- i. Selection and review of relevant agriculture, energy, and development-related spatial datasets;
- ii. Spatial overlay and filtering to identify areas with high agricultural activity and low electricity access;
- iii. Integration of infrastructure proximity and water resource indicators to assess electrification-enabled irrigation potential;
- iv. Incorporation of poverty and vulnerability indicators to support donor and concessional funding prioritization; and
- v. Interpretation and visualization of priority zones to support differentiated electrification planning.

2.2 Data Sources

The analysis utilized datasets available for Zambia. Key datasets included rainfed agriculture and irrigated agriculture as primary indicators of agricultural activity, population density, road network and proximity to financial institutions and existing electricity infrastructure. Surface water proximity was included to support assessment of irrigation potential. The Relative Wealth Index was incorporated as a proxy for development need and donor suitability. Solar, hydro, biomass and wind resource potential layers were included to assess the technical feasibility of off-grid and mini-grid solutions relevant to agricultural electrification.

Fig. 1 Rainfed crop production

Fig. 2 Irrigated crop production

2.3 Assumptions

Rainfed agricultural areas were assumed to represent zones with high potential for electrification enabled irrigation and climate resilient agricultural intensification, consistent with national priorities to expand irrigation and reduce vulnerability to climate variability. Irrigated agricultural areas were assumed to indicate zones with existing productive energy demand, where improved electricity access could enhance the efficiency and reliability of irrigation and water management systems and support the modernization of agricultural practices. A low Relative Wealth Index was applied to identify areas where affordability constraints justify donor and concessional financing

support. It was further assumed that proximity to existing grid infrastructure increases the feasibility of grid extension, while more remote areas are better suited for mini-grid or standalone renewable energy solutions.

2.4 Scenarios

2.4.1 Scenario 1

This scenario was designed to identify predominantly rural agricultural areas with limited electricity access and high need for concessional and donor-supported interventions.

- Priority given to unelectrified areas (mostly rural)
- High agricultural demand represented by areas with high rainfed crop production
- Low supply potential (10km+ away from existing grid and mini grid networks)
- Low RWI (-2 to 0) to represent affordability constraints and development need
- Proximity to surface waterways(0-5km)

2.4.1 Scenario 2

This scenario was designed to identify areas where existing agricultural activity and infrastructure conditions are more suitable for grid-based electrification interventions.

- Priority given to areas close to existing electrified zones (mostly urban and peri urban)
- High agricultural demand represented by areas with high irrigated crop production
- High supply potential (0-10km from existing grid network)
- Low RWI (-2 to 0) to reflect continued affordability constraints
- Proximity to surface waterways (0-5km) to support irrigation-related productive uses of electricity.

3. Results

3.1 Scenario 1

Fig. 3 Agricultural areas (/km²) with limited access to electricity

Fig. 4 Agricultural districts with limited access to electricity

The above figures show areas and districts with strong suitability for decentralized renewable energy solutions to support irrigation and supports targeting of rural electrification to improve climate resilience and productivity.

Fig. 5 Top areas to target electrification in in Scenario 1

3.2 Scenario 2

Fig. 6 Agricultural areas (/km²) with higher access to electricity

Fig. 7 Agricultural districts with higher access to electricity

The above figures show areas and districts suitable for grid extension and densification, combined with concessional and donor financing to improve irrigation efficiency, support agricultural commercialization and strengthen value chain development.

Fig. 8 Top areas to target electrification in Scenario 2

4. Discussion

The results demonstrate that targeted electrification can significantly support Zambia's agricultural growth and food security objectives through a combination of grid extension and densification, mini-grids, and standalone renewable energy solutions. The analysis highlights the importance of aligning electrification investments with agricultural activity, irrigation potential, and development need to maximize development impact.

4.1 Insights and Implications

Scenario 1 focuses on decentralized electrification in predominantly rural and rainfed agricultural areas with low electricity access and higher vulnerability. Under this scenario, mini-grids and standalone systems play a critical role in enabling irrigation expansion and productive uses of energy in remote farming communities. This approach is well suited for areas located far from existing grid infrastructure and supports climate-resilient agricultural intensification. It aligns strongly with rural electrification objectives and the need to improve agricultural productivity in underserved regions.

Scenario 2 encourages grid extension and densification in areas with existing irrigated agriculture and closer proximity to electricity infrastructure. This approach supports improved efficiency and reliability of irrigation systems and enables agro processing and other value adding activities. It aligns with national objectives to strengthen agricultural value chains and modernize farming systems. While this approach offers long term benefits in these areas, it may require significant infrastructure investment and may involve longer implementation timelines.

4.2 Policy Recommendations and Opportunities

To support agricultural growth in remote and rainfed farming areas, decentralized electrification solutions should be prioritized. In areas where grid extension and densification are feasible, targeted investment in transmission and distribution infrastructure is required to improve system reliability and support agricultural modernization.

Private sector participation remains critical in scaling up decentralized energy solutions. Strengthening incentives, risk-sharing mechanisms and concessional financing help attract private investment, particularly in high impact but lower income agricultural areas.

4.3 Limitations

- The analysis relied on open-source datasets, which may not fully reflect recent developments and current demand.
- Unavailability of important datasets such as hydrogeology, detailed land cover and soil type information limits the ability to fully assess crop suitability and irrigation feasibility.

4.4 Areas for Future Work

- Linking the analysis with the Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) least cost of electrification approach
- Strengthening coordination between energy and agriculture data management systems and institutional planning processes

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the value of geospatial analysis in supporting integrated planning for electrification, agricultural development and food security in Zambia. By combining data on agricultural activity, electricity access, infrastructure proximity, water resources and RWI, the analysis identifies priority areas where expanded electricity access can deliver the greatest agricultural and social benefits.

The findings highlight two complementary opportunity areas. Rainfed agricultural zones with low electricity access and higher vulnerability are well suited for off-grid and mini-grid solutions to support irrigation expansion and climate-resilient agricultural intensification. Irrigated areas located closer to existing grid infrastructure present opportunities for grid extension and densification to enhance irrigation performance and support agricultural modernization and value chain development.

The results underscore the importance of aligning electrification investments with national agricultural priorities and targeting donor and concessional financing to areas with high development impact and limited commercial viability. Overall, the study provides a practical, policy relevant framework to support coordinated action by government agencies, donors and development partners to strengthen agricultural productivity, rural livelihoods and food security through strategic electrification.

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